

1 **Axon guidance receptors have a specific function in endoderm fate choice of pluripotent stem**
2 **cells.**

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7 The organ systems of the human body are each derived from three germ layers: the endoderm,
8 mesoderm, and ectoderm. We defined here using transcriptomics a minimal set of components required or
9 important for germ layer fate choice to the endoderm in the first trimester of human development. We
10 describe a requirement for axon guidance receptors in germ layer lineage choice from pluripotent stem
11 cells in *Homo sapiens*, including Plxna3, Plxna4, Sema3e, Plxdc3, Efn5 and Plxna3.

12 Citations

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